

Effect of Work Motivation and Work Environment toward Employee Performance in the PDAM Tirta Malem Kabanjahe

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ABSTRACT

Work motivation in organizations is very important because the motivation has an important role in every individual, both in a leader and his subordinates, because this is one of the factors that is relied on in achieving an organizational goal where motivation is related to the strength or drive that is in a person so that it refers to the conditions that cause the diversity of intensity, quality, direction, and duration of work behavior. The work environment is also one part of the factors that can affect the process of employee performance, where if the work environment of an employee is not good and low employee motivation can certainly lead to low performance results of existing employees in the company, vice versa if the atmosphere a good work environment can certainly create good employee performance results. Therefore, in this study, the authors use work motivation and work environment as independent variables and employee performance as the dependent variable.

The population in this study was 115 people and 53 respondents. The method used in this research is quantitative with an associative approach. The technique used in this study is probability sampling with a simple random sampling approach. Data collection was carried out by distributing questionnaires to respondents who were PDAM Tirta Malem Kabanjahe employees. Data were analyzed using the validity test, reliability test, the classic assumption test, multiple linear regression analysis, t test, F test and test of determination R² which is operated by SPSS 16.

T test results in work motivation variables obtained t value of 5.530 > t table of 2.007 and work motivation correlated with employee performance by 55% so it can be concluded that part there is an influence between work motivation variables on employee performance variables, then t test results the work environment variables obtained t value of 3.582 > t table of 2.007 and the work environment correlated with employee performance of 35.6% so it can be concluded that part there is an influence between the work environment variables on employee performance variables. Based on the results of the hypothesis on the results of the F test obtained the calculated F value of 34.442 > F table of 3.18 so it can be concluded that the variables of work motivation and work environment together affect the employee performance variables. Test results The coefficient of determination (R²) obtained a value of R Square in 0.579. This means that work motivation and work environment variables affect employee performance by 57.9% and the remaining 42.1% is influenced by other variables not included in this study such as salary, leadership style, work discipline, workload, job satisfaction, awards, and so on.

KEYWORDS: *Work Motivation, Work Environment, Employee Performance*

1. Preliminary

Human resources are very important for the company in managing, managing and utilizing employees so that they can function productively to achieve the goals of a company. Human resources in the company need to be managed professionally so as to create a balance between the needs of employees with the demands and capabilities of the company's organization. This balance is the company's main key to developing productively. Achievement of organizational goals shows the results of work or work performance produced from employees in a company where the results of organizational work area obtained from a

series of activities carried out by the organization, organizational activities can be in the form of management of human resources in the organization and the work implementation process needed to achieve an organizational goal. To ensure that these activities can be in accordance with the expected results, management efforts are needed in the implementation of its activities so as to optimally improve employee performance in an effort to achieve a goal. According to Kasmir (2015), there are several factors that affect employee performance, including the factors of ability and expertise, knowledge, work design, personality,

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work motivation, leadership, leadership style, organizational culture, job satisfaction, work environment, loyalty, commitment, discipline work. To improve employee performance, it is necessary to pay attention to the causal factors, which means that each employee can make a separate contribution to performance, both employee performance and organizational performance, where each factor will certainly affect performance both directly and indirectly, one of which is a motivation where motivation is an effort to move employees, influence employees, support employees, direct employees, of course this can cause a person's behavior to be active in working and enthusiastic in achieving optimal results, in addition the company not only expects capable, capable, and skilled employees but also willing to work enterprising and eager to achieve maximum results. Employee's abilities and abilities are meaningless to the company if they don't want to work hard. PDAM Tirta Malem Kabanjahe is a company engaged in services which is to provide clean water services to the community in the Karo District area, and also meet the need for clean and healthy drinking water, while the purpose of PDAM Tirta Malem Kabanjahe is in addition to providing the best service and meeting the needs of clean water to the community in every village in the Karo District, PDAM Tirta Malem Kabanjahe is also useful for increasing the regional development of the Karo Regency in particular, where the income from the company's production will be deposited into the Karo district's regional treasury to increase regional income (PAD).

The main performance of the employees of PDAM Tirta Malem Kabanjahe is to provide the best service to the people of Karo Regency because it is undeniable that meeting the needs of the community is the key of the company. Based on research Tirta Malem Kabanjahe PDAM employees are still able to provide good work results where good service to the community, employee discipline over time, good working relationships between leaders and subordinates, adequate work environment and employees are able to complete work on time, in this case, of course the company's vision and mission can run well and in accordance with company expectations to provide the best service to the community as well as providing clean and healthy water to the community especially in Karo Regency. To support a better performance process, naturally there is a need for readiness, skills and expertise of good human resources such as guidance, training and evaluation so that the performance of employees in the company is in line with expectations.

The work environment is one part of the factors that can affect the process of employee performance, where the work environment of an employee is not good and low employee motivation can certainly result in a low result of the performance of employees in the company, vice versa if the working environment A good one can certainly create good employee performance because the work environment is a condition and atmosphere that can affect one's performance processes.

Work motivation in organizations is very important where, motivation is one aspect that is very influential on the performance of an organization where motivation is related to the strength or encouragement that exists in a person so that it points to the conditions that cause the diversity of intensity, quality, direction and duration work behavior.

Motivation can be interpreted as a person's strength or drive that can lead to a level of perseverance and enthusiasm in carrying out an activity, both sourced from within and from outside. Motivation has an important role in every individual, both in a leader and his subordinates because this is one of the factors that is relied on in achieving an organizational goal, where motivation can encourage each individual or employee to work hard and enthusiastically to achieve good results.

In a company of myriad aspects of -aspect that can support or encourage walking and yes sue two companies among others with their employees, equipment, and the working environment was good. Of course, this needs to be taken into account so that the achievement of goals in the company can run well because the work environment is very influential on the work performance of employees in a company/agency, by observing the work environment can certainly increase employee morale in working to achieve a the destination. If employee motivation increases, employee performance will automatically increase. If this can go well, the achievement of the goals of a company will run well.

From the description of the background of the problem above the writer then conducts research to examine in more depth about "**The Effect of Work Motivation and Work Environment on Employee Performance in PDAM Tirta Malem Kabanjahe**".

2. Formulation of the Problem

Air city background above, so in this study, the authors me the formula k an issue as follows:

- A. Does work motivation affect employee performance at PDAM Tirta Malem Kabanjahe?
- B. Does the work environment affect the performance of employees at PDAM Tirta Malem Kabanjahe?
- C. Do work motivation and work environment simultaneously affect the performance of employees at PDAM Tirta Malem Kabanjahe?

3. Research Objectives

The research objectives include:

- A. To determine the effect of work motivation on employee performance in PDAM Tirta Malem Kabanjahe.
- B. To determine the effect of the work environment on employee performance at PDAM Tirta Malem Kabanjahe.
- C. To determine the effect of work motivation and work environment simultaneously on employee performance at PDAM Tirta Malem Kabanjahe.
- D. To comply with one earned S Arjana Management at Sekolah Tinggi ILMU Ekonomi LMII Medan.

4. Research Benefits

- A. For the writer is to be practice con theories that have been acquired during his lectures so that the author can add a practical knowledge of the issues faced by the company.
- B. For company that results of this study are expected to contribute ideas that can be used as consideration for the company in addressing human resource issues related to work motivation, work environment, and employee performance.

C. For academics, the results of this research are expected to help the learning process and the application of specific knowledge of the science of human resource management and can be a reference for further research with the same theme.

5. Work motivation

According to Mangkunegara (2011), motivation is a condition that drives the beginning to be able to achieve the goals of his motives. " In this case, motives mean they will or goals to be achieved ".

According to Sutrisno (2016), work motivation is a factor that drives a person to do a certain activity, therefore motivation is often interpreted as a factor driving one's behavior.

6. Work environment

According to Nitisebito (2018), the work environment is everything that is around workers and that can influence themselves in carrying out the tasks that they are charged. According to Sunyoto (2013) cited by Supriyanto, and Mukzam (2018), the work environment is something that exists around workers who can influence themselves in carrying out the tasks that they are charged.

9. Prior Researchers

Previous research is used as a basis in the preparation of research, where the aim is to find out the results that have been done by previous researchers, as well as comparisons and images that can support subsequent similar studies. The previous studies can be seen in the following table.

7. Employee performance

According to Kasmir (2015), performance is the result of work and work behavior that has been achieved in completing tasks and responsibilities given within a certain period.

According Mangkunegara (2011), the employee's performance is the performance that comes from k in Gov someone in quality and count it as achieved by employees in Mel aksanakan duties and responsibilities given.

8. Framework

Based on the explanation of the previous theory, the researcher draws a picture of the mind framework as follows. Illustrate the relationship of variable all independent that work motivation (X₁), work environment (X₂), to variation dependent that employee performance (Y).

No	Researcher's name	Title Research	Methods Research	Result
1	Eliyanto (2018)	The influence of work motivation and work environment on the performance of Muhammadiyah High School Teachers Kab. Kebumen.	Data collection using a questionnaire, and data analysis using descriptive analysis, multiple linear regression analysis, t test, and F test.	Work motivation and work environment together have a significant effect on the performance of Muhammadiyah High School teachers in Kebumen Regency, because the significance value of F is 0,000 less than $\alpha = 0.05$ (0,000 0.05) and is able to contribute to the teacher performance variable 0.726 or 72.6%, while the remaining 27.4% is influenced by other variables not examined in this study.
2	Supriyanto dan Mukzam (2018)	Effect of motivation work and work environment on the performance of employees at the RRI Station Malang Public Broadcasting.	This research a type of explanatory research with a quantitative approach. Analytical methods used in this research are multiple linear regression analysis.	Results Regression analysis, work motivation and work environment on LPP RRI Malang Station have an influence simultaneous and partial positive and significant impact on employee performance.
3	Murdiyanto (2012)	The influence of motivation and work environment on hepy motorcycle employee performance Cabang Jawa Tengah.	Test Results Independent statistical t-test sample.	The testing hypothesis of the influence of work motivation on Employee Performance can be partially concluded The work Motivation variable has a significant positive effect on employee performance variables. Testing the hypothesis of the influence of the Work Environment on Employee Performance can be partially concluded Work Environment variables significant positive effect on variables performance of employees. Results R Square of 0.76 this means that 76% variation in Employee Performance can be

				explained by variations of the two independent variables Work Motivation and Work Environment. While the rest is equal to 24% is explained by other causes outside the model.
4	Kholil (2015)	The effect of work motivation and work environment on the performance of employees in the Malang Regency Industry and Trade Office.	The analysis used includes the instrument test, classical assumption test, normality test, multiple regression, linear tests, hypothesis testing and coefficient of determination tests using multiple linear regression analysis.	The results showed that work motivation had a significant effect on the performance of Malang Regency Industry and Trade Department employees, the work environment had a significant effect on the performance of Malang Regency Industry and Trade Service employees, work motivation and work environment together influenced the performance of Malang Regency Industry and Trade Service employees.

10. Premise

The premise is a foundation that is right and is used to draw conclusions that can be accepted by others. The premise is also the basis for the formation of theories and research results relating to research being conducted by researchers, among others:

- A. Eliyanto (2018), explained that work motivation (X_1) and work environment (X_2) together had a significant effect on the performance (Y) of Muhammadiyah High School Teachers in Kebumen Regency.
- B. Supriyanto, and Mukzam (2018), explained that work motivation (X_1) and work environment (X_2) had a simultaneous influence on employee performance (Y) on the LPP RRI Malang Station.
- C. Murdiyanto (2012), explained that work motivation (X_1) and work environment (X_2) together had a significant effect on employee performance (Y) of the Central Java Motor Hepy Branch.
- D. Kholil (2015), explained that work motivation (X_1) and work environment (X_2) jointly affect the performance of employees (Y) in the Department of Industry and Trade of Malang Regency.

11. Research Hypothesis

Based on the description of the framework and the results of the study above, the researchers propose several hypotheses in this study as follows:

1. Work motivation has an influence on employee performance at PDAM Tirta Malem Kabanjahe.
2. The work environment has an influence on employee performance at PDAM Tirta Malem Kabanjahe.
3. Work motivation and work environment simultaneously have an influence on employee performance at PDAM Tirta Malem Kabanjahe.

12. Research methodology

12.1. Types of Research

The type of research used in this study is the quantitative method. According to Melva and Togu (2011), quantitative research methods are research methods based on positive things that use certain populations and samples as well as the techniques used in random sampling, data collection using research instruments and in analyzing data using statistical analysis tools that will answer a hypothesis. Quantitative methods aim to determine the relationship between two or more variables. Where the independent variable is work motivation (X_1) and work environment (X_2), while the dependent variable is employee performance (Y). In this form of associative research it can be seen the effect of work motivation and work environment on employee performance.

12.2. Location and Time of Research

Location is a place or area to conduct research to obtain the required data. The location in this study is in Jln. Letjen Jamin Ginting No. 11A, KP. In, Kabanjahe, Karo Regency, North Sumatra 22111. When the study was scheduled at the time of the activity or the lengthy process of research activities carried out. When this research was conducted in June to September 2019.

12.3. Population and Sample

Population is a combination of all elements in the form of events, things or other people who have similar characteristics that are the center of attention of a researcher because it is seen as research. According to Sugiyono (2017), population is a generalized area consisting of objects/subjects that have certain characteristics determined by researchers to be studied and then drawn conclusions. As for the population of this study is the Tirta Malem Kabanjahe PDAM Employee where the population is 115 employees. Where there are 78 male, males, 37 females, 31 S1 graduates and 84 high school graduates.

In gathering data that has a very large number it is very difficult because it relates to time, cost, data analysis tools, therefore to facilitate data collection the authors make a sample as a representative population. According to Sugiyono (2017), the sample is part of the number and characteristics possessed by the population. If the population is large, and researchers may not study everything in the population, for example, due to limited funds, manpower and time, then researchers can use samples taken from that population.

The technique used in this study is the technique probability sampling approach to simple random sampling (simple random sample). According to Sugiyono (20 07) cited by Togu and Melva (2011), probability sampling is a sampling withdrawal technique that provides equal opportunities and for all members of the population to be elected as sample members. Then explain that simple random sampling is a way or method of taking samples from existing populations that are carried out randomly without regard to the levels that exist in these elements of the population. In this study, taking the number of respondents using the formula S loving and with an error rate of 1%, 5% and 10%. (Isaac and Michael in Sugiyono, 2017). Researchers use an error rate of 10%.

$$n = \frac{115}{1 + (115 \times (0.1)^2)}$$

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

$$n = \frac{115}{1 + (115 \times 0.01)}$$

$$n = \frac{115}{1 + 1.15}$$

$$n = \frac{115}{2.15}$$

$$n = 53,4883721$$

$$n = 53$$

Information:

n = Sample Size

N = Population Size

e = tolerated error rate (10% = 0.1)

Where the number of sample elements that must be taken from the population of Tirta Malem Kabanjahe employees is 53 employees.

12.4. Data Collection Techniques

According to Melva and Togu (2012), data collection techniques are a method or research technique used in the process of collecting data which is a collection of research materials available from various sources to be used in answering problems for a phenomenon that is happening. The data collection techniques used in this study are:

A. Primary data

Primary data is data obtained directly from research sources in the form of interview questionnaire results. According to Sugiyono (2017), primary data is a data source that directly provides data to data collectors. The primary data collection in this study is by distributing questionnaires, conducting observations or observing activities directly, and conducting interviews directly with PDAM Tirta Malem Kabanjahe employees.

B. Secondary Data

Secondary data is data that is collected or obtained indirectly from its source or data that is owned by organizations/agencies, journals, previous research, and literature studies related to the title of the research. Secondary data in the form of number of employees, absenteeism and organizational profile. According to Sugiyono (2017), secondary data is a source that does not directly provide data to data collectors, for example through other people or through documents.

13. Research Results and Discussion

13.1. Validity Test

Item-Total Statistics				
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
W. Motivation1	113.27	66,616	.712	.931
W. Motivation2	113.23	67,495	.575	.933
W. Motivation3	113.20	69,062	.362	.935
W. Motivation4	113.13	68,257	.449	.934
W. Motivation5	113.10	66,852	.543	.933
W. Motivation6	113.23	65,840	.689	.931
W. Motivation7	113.20	66,441	.697	.931
W. Motivation8	113.20	67,545	.555	.933
W. Motivation9	113.23	67,495	.575	.933
W. Environment1	113.33	66,713	.562	.933
W. Environment2	113.37	66,861	.651	.932
W. Environment3	113.23	67,633	.557	.933
W. Environment4	113.20	67,683	.537	.933
W. Environment5	113.20	66,372	.549	.933
W. Environment6	113.23	66,323	.633	.932
W. Environment7	113.20	66,510	.688	.931

W. Environment8	113.20	66,510	688	.931
W. Environment9	113.10	67,128	586	.933
W. Environment10	113.27	67,237	.628	.932
E. Performance1	113.23	67,220	.611	.932
E. Performance2	113.23	67,564	.566	.933
E. Performance3	113.20	67,269	.513	.934
E. Performance4	113.13	67,706	.518	.933
E. Performance5	113.13	67,568	.467	.934
E. Performance6	113.23	67,426	.504	.934
E. Performance7	113.23	67,426	.504	.934
E. Performance8	113.20	66,786	.568	.933

From the results of the SPSS 16 program output on Item-Total Statistics it can be seen that the value of Corrected item-total Correlation is greater than r table, which means that the value of each statement attribute is greater than 0.349 so it can be concluded that the statement is valid. (Ghozali, 2016).

13.2. Test Reliability

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.935	27

From the results of the SPSS 16 program output on Reliability Statistics it can be seen that the Cronbach's Alpha value is 0.935 which means it is greater than 0.70 thus it can be concluded that the measuring instrument is reliable. (Nunnally, 1994 in Ghozali, 2016).

13.3. Classical Assumption Test Results

13.3.1. Normality Test

Normal P-P Plot of Regression Standardized Residual

According Ghozali (2016), if of data spread around the diagonal line and follow the direction of the diagonal line or histogram graph showing a normal distribution pattern, then the regression model to meet the assumption of normality. Based on the results of the SPSS 16 program output on the Normal PP Plot of Regression Standardized Residual, it can be seen that the data spreads around the diagonal line and follows the direction of the diagonal line showing normal distribution patterns so that the normality test is fulfilled.

13.3.2. Multicollinearity Test

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	2.920	3.828		.763	.449		
	W. Motivation	.508	.092	.550	5.530	.000	.852	1.174
	W. Environment	.288	.080	.356	3.582	.001	.852	1.174

According to Ghozali (2016), the cutoff value, commonly used to indicate multicollinearity is a tolerance value ≤ 0.10 or equal to a VIF value ≥ 10 . Based on the results of SPSS 16 output on Coefficients it can be seen that the coefficient of 1.174 10 it can be concluded that multicollinearity does not occur so it can be concluded that the data used passes classical assumptions because multicollinearity does not occur.

13.3.3. Heteroscedasticity Test

From the results of SPSS 16 output on the Scatterplot image it can be seen that the points spread randomly and spread both above and below the number 0 on the Y axis. It can be concluded that there was no heteroscedasticity in the regression model. (Ghozali, 2016).

13.4. Results of Multiple Linear Regression

Model		Coefficients ^a					Collinearity Statistics	
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Tolerance	VIF
		B	Std. Error	Beta				
1	(Constant)	2.920	3.828		.763	.449		
	W. Motivation	.508	.092	.550	5.530	.000	.852	1.174
	W. Environment	.288	.080	.356	3.582	.001	.852	1.174

Based on the results of the SPSS 16 program output on Coefficients describe the regression equation, namely:
 $Y = 2,920 + 0.508 X_1 + 0.288 X_2$

Where:

- a: The constant number of Unstandardized Coefficients is 2,920
- B 1: The first regression coefficient number at X₁ (Work Motivation) is 0.508.
- B 2: The second regression coefficient number at X₂ (Work Environment) is 0.288.

13.5. Hypothesis Test Results

13.5.1. Effect of Work Motivation (X 1) On Employee Performance (Y)

Model		Coefficients ^a					Collinearity Statistics	
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Tolerance	VIF
		B	Std. Error	Beta				
1	(Constant)	2.920	3.828		.763	.449		
	W. Motivation	.508	.092	.550	5.530	.000	.852	1.174
	W. Environment	.288	.080	.356	3.582	.001	.852	1.174

From the results of the SPSS 16 program output in the Coefficients table for the first regression coefficient work motivation variable shows the results of the t value of 5.530 > t table of 2.007 so that H1 is accepted and H0 is rejected and work motivation correlates with employee performance by 55%. This means that part there is the influence of work motivation on employee performance.

13.5.2. Effect on Work Environment (X2) on Employee Performance (Y)

Model		Coefficients ^a					Collinearity Statistics	
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Tolerance	VIF
		B	Std. Error	Beta				
1	(Constant)	2.920	3.828		.763	.449		
	W. Motivation	.508	.092	.550	5.530	.000	.852	1.174
	W. Environment	.288	.080	.356	3.582	.001	.852	1.174

From the output of the SPSS 16 program output on Coefficients for the regression coefficients of the two work environment variables showed the results of the t value of 3.582 > t table of 2.007 so that H1 was accepted and H0 was rejected and the work environment correlated with employee performance of 35.6%. This means that there is a partial influence of the work environment on employee performance.

13.5.3. Effect of Work Motivation (X1) and Work Environment (X2) on Employee Performance (Y)

ANOVA ^b						
	Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	295.851	2	147.925	34.429	.000 ^a
	Residual	214.829	50	4.297		
	Total	510.679	52			

From the results of the SPSS 16 program output on Anova table can be seen the calculated F value of 34.442 > F table of 3.18 so that H₀ is rejected and H₁ is accepted. This means that the independent variables of work motivation and work environment together influence the dependent variable of employee performance.

13.6. Coefficients of determination R²

Model Summary ^b									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.761 ^a	.579	.563	2.073	.579	34.429	2	50	.000

From the results of the SPSS 16 program output in the Summary Model table it can be seen the R Square value of 0.579 or 57.9%. This means that the independent variables of work motivation and work environment affect the dependent variable of employee performance by 57.9% and the remaining 42.1% is influenced by other factors, not examined in this study such as salary, leadership style, work discipline and so forth.

14. Conclusion

Based on the results of research that aims to determine "The Effect of Work Motivation and Work Environment on Employee Performance in PDAM Tirta Malem Kabanjahe". Based on research and data processing results that have been carried out in this study, the following conclusions are obtained:

- Based on the results of the hypothesis test it is known that the variable of work motivation influences employee performance. It can be seen that $t_{arithmatic} > t_{table}$ or $5.530 > 2.007$ and work motivation correlates with employee performance by 55%, so it can be concluded that part there is an influence between variables work motivation on employee performance variables.
- Based on the results of the hypothesis test it is known that the work environment variables affect the performance of employees, this can be seen that $t_{count} > t_{table}$ or $3.582 > 2.007$ and the work environment correlates with employee performance of 35.6%, so it can be concluded that parted there is influence between the working environment variable to variable employee performance.
- Based on the results of testing the hypothesis of the F test results obtained value of F count equal to $34.429 > F_{table}$ by 3.18 so that it can be concluded that work motivation and work environments e cara together have an effect on the variable employee performance.
- Based on the test results of the coefficient of determination (R₂) obtained a value of R Square in 0, 579. This means that work motivation and work environment variables affect employee performance by 57.9 % and the remaining 42.1 % is influenced by other variables not included in this study such as salary, leadership style, work discipline and so forth.

15. Suggestion

After conducting research, discussion and drawing conclusions obtained from the results of the study, the authors as researchers can provide suggestions relating to research as follows:

- PDAM Tirta Malem Kabanjahe still have to do enhancement, employee performance through the provision of employment to the employee motivation which can lead to the employee's performance was good in the future.
- PDAM Tirta Malem Kabajahe must pay attention to the work environment so that it can provide a sense of security at work such as paying attention to infrastructure facilities, both office conditions, colors in office space, with the aim of producing good employee performance in the future.
- The results of this study can be used as a recommendation for future researchers to conduct research in different places.

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